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EXPLORING THE BIOMOLECULAR ASPECTS OF PHYSICAL REHABILITATION INVOLVED IN THE MANAGEMENT OF PHYSICALLY INACTIVE PATIENTS

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Abstract

Physical rehabilitation has a key role in the management of patients with disabilities due to age-related muscle loss or who suffered catastrophic events such as surgery, trauma, cancer or other severe illnesses. All of these instances have in common a period of extended physical inactivity. After prolonged bed rest, a number of complications typically occur; the first of which is muscle loss that can worsen existing conditions caused by sarcopenia which in turn leads to the loss of physical functions. Here we review some of the main strategies adopted by physiotherapists and nutrition specialists for the management of physically inactive patients regardless of the causes leading to their prolonged bed rest. Biomolecular aspects associated to physical rehabilitation are also explored in the context of physical therapy, forest-bathing as well as body self-healing that can be facilitated by mechanical stimuli through physiotherapy, but which is also aided by an appropriate diet and nature-based therapy.

Keywords: physical rehabilitation; physiotherapy; biomolecular mechanisms; biotechnology; physical inactivity; nutrition.

Introduction

Individuals are defined as physically inactive when they spend less than two and half hours per week participating in moderately intense activity. A significantly high percentage of the general population of the modern Western world falls into this category which is typically due to poor lifestyle habits. This lack of exercise can have a whole host of negative impacts on cardiovascular functions and metabolism which in turn increases the risk of developing various disabilities as people age [1].

However, there are several other causes other than simply having a sedentary lifestyle which can lead to involuntary physical inactivity including prolonged post-operative hospitalization, trauma, and cancer [2-5]. Among them, cancer is a highly socially relevant disease affecting the general population (accounting for 1 in 6 deaths worldwide <https://www.cancer.org/research/cancer-facts-statistics/all-cancer-facts-figures/cancer-facts-figures-2022.html> Cancer Facts & Figures 2022, accessed on May 3rd, 2022) but which can also

impact the ability of its survivors to partake in physical activity. This is the case for adult survivors of childhood acute lymphoblastic leukemia which have been reported as less likely to be active than the wider population [5].

After a period of prolonged bed rest, a number of complications may typically occur; the first of which is muscle loss that can worsen existing conditions caused by sarcopenia which in turn may lead to disabilities, especially among the elderly [6]. In this context, physical rehabilitation is a first-line treatment strategy for patients with a history of physical inactivity and consequent loss of physical functions. The role of physiotherapists in sustaining the body's self-healing capability is clearly fundamental and should be accompanied by a correct diet (including high-quality protein intake aiming i.e. at limiting muscle loss) and nature-inspired practices which can have beneficial effects such as stimulating the immune system and shortening healing times [6].

Objectives

We aim at summarizing the main strategies that can be adopted for the management of physically inactive patients regardless of the causes leading to prolonged bed rest. Other goals for this review include the discussion of some biomolecular mechanisms associated to physical rehabilitation, as well as the role of physiotherapy, together with an appropriate diet and nature-based therapies such as forest-bathing in promoting the body's ability to self-heal.

Materials and methods

We explored the recent scientific literature relating to themes reported in the Objectives section, as well as the keywords 'physical rehabilitation; physiotherapy; biomolecular mechanisms; biotechnology; physical inactivity; nutrition'. To this purpose, we used scientific search engines such as, PubMed and Google Scholar. In our search we excluded retracted publications and non-English articles.

Results and Discussion

Progression of aging, especially in individuals with a sedentary lifestyle, but also in those who have experienced catastrophic events such as injury, cancer or other severe diseases, may determine prolonged physical inactivity (Figure 1) that is associated to protein catabolism and consequent loss of lean body mass typical of sarcopenia. [7] This is due to the chronic imbalance between the new synthesis of muscle proteins and their breakdown which is experienced during a period of physical inactivity coupled with the presence of illness or trauma which may also significantly accelerate the rate of muscle protein catabolism. [7]

The physiotherapist's role in treating sarcopenia is clearly fundamental (Figure 1) as patients, including older adults, with sarcopenia can significantly benefit from a mixed exercise program even for periods as short as 14 days by improving their gait speed and other day to day activities [8]. An adjunct to physiotherapy is massage which has an important role in sports performance and rehabilitation[9] and may also sustain the body's self-healing capability after traumatic events[10].

From a biomechanical point of view, the human body continuously regenerates thanks to the action of adult stem cells; undifferentiated elements possessing the unique ability to self-renew or differentiate to maintain the integrity of the different tissues. Their interaction with the extracellular matrix is crucial in influencing the mechanical properties, such as cytoskeleton plasticity and remodelling, involved in wound healing. It is well known that mechanical and physical stimuli are able to modulate stem cells fate in their own niche, and improve intrinsic

body self-healing abilities, without the need for more invasive interventions such as stem cell transplantation [11]. Artificially stimulated secretion of growth factors from bone marrow mesenchymal stem cells (BM-MSCs) may regulate the inflammatory environment by inhibiting the expression of M1 macrophages and promoting the expression of M2 macrophages, resulting in enhanced wound healing [12].

As for the importance of nutrition in healing after traumatic events and slow sarcopenia, a correct diet revealed a first-line strategy to prevent muscle catabolism and promote the anabolism processes in bed rest studies conducted on healthy volunteers [7]. These studies revealed the importance of dietary-derived amino acids as prerequisites for inducing the synthesis of muscle proteins in the individuals examined. Amino acid supplementation and a high-quality protein intake of 25-30 g with each meal [6] are crucial in the maintenance of muscle mass during medically mandated and age-related physical inactivity.[7]

Another aspect worth mentioning is the importance of spending time in nature to accelerate healing after trauma. Forest bathing in particular is a nature-inspired practice which is gaining scientific interest for its many important therapeutic applications for human health, both mental and physical[13]. The benefits mostly stem from inhalable compounds that can have invigorating effects on the immune system [13]. Interestingly, some plant-derived volatile organic compounds (VOCs), such as terpinolene and α -phellandrene, were also found to contribute in vitro to wound healing by attenuating inflammation and oxidative stress [14]. Forest bathing, or forest therapy, sessions could also be tailored to the specific causes of inactivity whether it be depression or cancer [15]. Regardless of the underlying issue, spending time mindfully immersed in nature inhaling and absorbing biogenic VOCs through sebaceous glands on the skin lowers cortisol levels and boosts the body's ability to heal [16].

Figure 1 Schematic representation of the main issue (complications of multicausal physical inactivity) and the main patients' management strategies described in this review

Conclusion

Physiotherapists play a fundamental role in the management of physically-inactive patients whose functional loss may stem from a multitude of circumstances such as surgery, trauma, cancer, aging and a sedentary lifestyle. The common denominator for all of these circumstances is of course a lack of physical activity. Prolonged hospitalization or bed rest after trauma may cause debilitating complications associated to muscle loss, or sarcopenia, which in turn lead to the loss of physical functions and in some cases physical disability. Physiotherapists, nutrition specialists as well as nature-inspired therapists should work together for the holistic management of such patients regardless of the etiology leading to their prolonged physical inactivity. Numerous proteins, and especially growth factors, are involved in the adult stem cell-mediated biomolecular mechanisms associated to regeneration. Physiotherapy which includes exercises of moderate intensity, an appropriate diet rich in high-quality nutrients (especially high-quality proteins) and nature-based therapy such as forest-bathing with exposure to biogenic volatile organic compounds, can all combine to further aid in the rehabilitation process.

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